

URBANISATION ANALYSIS USING SPATIALSUPPORT AND IMPROVED RANDOM FOREST DECISION TREE APPROACH

Dr. K. Shunmugapriya* & P. Prasath**

* Head & Associate Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur, Tamilnadu

** Assistant Engineer, Rural Development and Panchayat, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

Urbanization is the major strategy that leads to the loss of the various biodiversity and the homogenization of geological habitat. But due to the heterogeneity of these their spatial extent, is difficult to quantify and monitor. Since vegetation in urban areas delivers crucial ecological services as a support to human well-being and to the urban population in general, its monitoring is a major issue for urban planners. It is necessary to study and analyse the drastic changes occurred due to global urbanization periodically. Monitoring the changes in urban green spaces are their functions such as the management of air, climate and water quality, the reduction of noise, the protection of species and the development of recreational activities The periodical assessment of urbanization gives raise to the development of various techniques and rules from several researchers. This paper is also a part of development over the urban-land cover analysis. It introduces an improved Budget based node calculation in Decision tree approach that preserves the statistical features and object boundaries and help in improving the classification accuracy. The system implements a spectral bands segmentation method, which differentiates the remote sensory images as Land Cover (LC) and Land Use (LU). The proposed RF algorithm of decision trees attempts to provide an improved efficiency over the other existing methods that is obtained from the experimental verification of the earlier algorithms with the proposed. The comparison report shows the performance of the algorithm from 2007 to 2013 respectively.

1. Introduction:

The population increase and migration of people from rural areas is the reason for drastic change in land cover areas and water surfaces that leads to urban development. The Urban development has been motivated in high rate by the growth of infrastructures, buildings, real estates and housing, sanitarries, utility grids and transport systems. It is necessary to study and analyse the changes occurred due to the rapid development in a country or a state, which is made possible by adopting a remote sensing method Urban-rural land use change is a very important phenomenon, which characterizes the urban and sub-urban areas surrounding the cities and oasis in the desert and arid zones, due mainly to urbanization activities, resulting from demographic and industrial development and also from immigration. Urbanization is considered to be an important issue and its impact on the agricultural lands surrounding urban areas has to be studied. The urban growth process is accompanied by the modification or reduction of various portions of the city being part of a pre-existing landscape; therefore, fragmentation is the most obvious symptom of a time series that eventually leads to disorganization of an urban area. The construction of a road can be seen, at an embryonic stage, as an insignificant process: however, over the years, this may affect the land cover as well as paving the way for new urban settlements, resulting in geographic fragmentation and new structural patches spread over the area of interest. In Italy, cities continue to enlarge their boundaries, even if their growth is in general accompanied by environmental degradation, drastic reduction of agricultural crops, pastures, green areas and loss of biodiversity. According to data from the Italian Institute of Statistics, it is possible to point out the continuing loss of the "free surface" parameter, term here used to describe fields, grasslands, forests or areas not occupied by human artefacts such as buildings, factories, urban infrastructure, etc. Urbanization is inevitable, when pressure on land is high, agriculture incomes are low and population increases are excessive, as is the case in most of the developing countries of the world.

In a way urbanization is desirable for human development On the other hand, uninhibited urbanization has been in authority for many of the difficulties, our cities experiences today, resultant in insufficient living environment, acute harms of drinking water, noise and air pollution, disposal of waste, traffic congestion etc. To develop these environmental humiliations in and around the cities, the technical development in relevant fields have to cracked these problems instigated by rapid urbanization, only then the results of development will spread most of the depressed ones. The recent technology of remote sensing which contains both aerial as well as satellite based systems, allow us to gather lot of physical data rather simply, with speed and on tedious basis, and organized with GIS assists us to examine the data spatially, offering prospects of producing various options, thereby enhancing the whole scheduling process.

1.1 Objectives:

The main objectives behind the research is given below,

- ✓ To introduce a pattern based recognition and classification of objects with respect to its urban and forest land use classes by the presentation of heterogeneous and effective algorithm design.
- ✓ To understand, evaluate and represent the variation occurred in the urban ecosystem periodically with the inclusion of extreme automated segmentation architecture from the research.
- ✓ To encourage a global perception with the help of pattern selection and organization mechanism that helps to differentiate the land, water-bodies and forest vegetation easily.
- ✓ The other objectives related to the study are
 - To create a land use land cover classification scheme
 - To determine the trend, nature, rate, location and magnitude of land use and Land cover change.
 - To forecast the future pattern of land use land cover in the area.
 - To generate data on land consumption rate and land absorption coefficient since more emphasis is placed on built-up land.
 - To evaluate the socio-economic implications of predicted change

2. Study Area and Site Description:

Urban areas have been recognized as “engines of inclusive economic growth”. Of the 121 crores Indians, 83.3 crores live in rural areas while 37.7 crores stay in urban areas i.e. approximately 32% of the population due to globalization. It is because the better opportunities those cities provide for individual development and that there are very few occupational choices available in the villages. Cities are the better equipped habitat to provide livelihood opportunities. Satisfying people’s day today needs is still a challenging task in metro cities, that too in and around South India. We can say that, people will have a tendency of migrating to cities as long as cities provide better lifestyle and employment opportunities. Hyderabad is the one of the fastest growing city in southern India. Hyderabad is one of the major metropolitan cities visibly developed a lot. In 1869, Hyderabad Municipal Corporation was introduced by British Government so as monitor population growth in Hyderabad due to the urban development. Hyderabad is the capital city of Telangana and its geographical coordinates are from 17.3850° north to 78.4867° east. The city is divided into 4 major sub-urban regions and each sub-urban region is divided into five divisions for official use. Many investigations were performed as a case study on Hyderabad region.

3 Methodologies:

The methodology employed in this research focus on the measurement of area that is differentiated as LU and LC regions. The LU/LC pattern of a region is an outcome of natural and socio-economic factors and their utilization by man in time and space. Land is becoming a scarce resource due to immense agricultural and demographic pressure. Hence, information and possibilities for their optimal use is essential for the selection, planning and implementation of land use schemes to meet the increasing demands for basic human needs and welfare. This information also assists in monitoring the dynamics of land use resulting out of changing demands of increasing population. LU/LC change has become a central component in current strategies for managing natural resources and monitoring environmental changes. The advancement in the concept of vegetation mapping has greatly increased research on land use land cover change thus providing an accurate evaluation of the spread and health of the world’s forest, grassland, and agricultural resources has become an important priority. Viewing the Earth from space is now crucial to the understanding of the influence of man’s activities on his natural resource base over time.

Figure 1: Flowchart

4. Result and Discussion:

The analysis process of urbanization using the proposed Improved Random Forest DT algorithm provides increased accuracy of identifying the LC and LU regions than the all other approaches developed earlier. The spectral and texture attributes are calculated for further differentiating the band levels found in the image sample.

4.1 Data Collection:

In this research, an experiment is made on two images containing all the attributes required to classify, which consist of two random years 2007 and 2013 from the database USGS Earth Explorer website respectively shown in Fig.1, 2. The USGS Earth explorer containing the spectral view of Cloud Free Landsat satellite data of Hyderabad region is considered

No.	Image taken on	Satellite/ sensor	Reference system/ path/ Row
1	February 2007	Landsat5 /TM	WRS-2/144/48
2	February 2013	Landsat7 /ETM+	WRS-2/144/48

Table.1. Details of Landsat data collected

The below two images Fig 1 and 2 shows the spectral view of the selected two random years 2007 and 2013

Figure 1: Ariel view of 2007 satellite image Fig 2. Ariel view of 2013 satellite image

The spectral training images Fig. 1, 2 are passed into a series of process such as pre-processing of training and test data, Identification of classes, Segmentation of the data, and classification results, which are all performed for finding the accuracy of detecting the LC and LU data.

4.2 Class Selection:

In this experiment, Land cover regions are denoted by the Built up area and Barren land, whereas the Land use regions are denoted by the Vegetation and Water bodies that is applicable for both the 2007 and 2013 satellite images

4.3 Pre-Processing Of Training and Test Data:

The intensity values are detected from the Figure 1, 2 based on the RGB value calculation method, which are used for adjusting the pixels of the attributes present in the image. The enhanced image is provided with a legible quality of RGB existence and a noise free data. In fig 3, the improved spectral view of 2007 year is represented; likewise the enhancement is performed for Fig. 2 of 2013 spectral image.

Figure 3: Enhanced spectral image of 2007

4.4 Segmentation Results:

The attributes classes are segmented into four bands denoting the spectral intensities of the RGB values such as Near Infra-red (Near IR), Short IR1, Short IR2, and Thermal IR shown in Fig. 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9. From these four spectral bands, two bands may not be considered by our proposed method. The short IR1 and short IR2 from 2007 and 2013 is considered less, whereas the other bands are analyzed to follow up classification

Figure 4: Near IR representation of 2007

Figure 5: Near IR representation of 2013

Figure 6: Short IR1 representation of 2007

Figure 7: Short IR1 representation of 2013

Figure 8: Short IR2 representation of 2007

Figure 9: Short IR2 representation of 2013

Figure 10: Thermal IR representation of 2007

Figure 11: Thermal IR representation of 2013

As a result, the derived bands were used as the dependent variables whereas the land cover classes were used as the independent variables.

4.5 Classes:

In addition, the spectral band results are identified and the attributes classes are separated from it, showing the water bodies, forest, urban lands and bare lands. The below figs. 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19 represents the fine definition of the attributes classes for 2007 and 2013 discussed above

Figure 12: Water bodies representation of 2007

Figure 13: Water bodies representation of 2013

Figure 14: Forest representation of 2007

Figure 15: Forest representation of 2013

Figure 16: Urban land representation of 2007

Figure 17: Urban land representation of 2013

Figure 18: Bare land representation of 2007

Figure 19: Bare land representation of 2013

4.6 Classification Results:

The DT based classification is applied in the segmented images to derive the LC and LU region view that is mentioned in the below Figs. 20, 21, 22, 23 of the years 2007 and 2013.

Figure 20: LC representation of 2007 spectral image

Figure 21: LC representation of 2013 spectral image

The LC and LU is identified by applying this technique with the implementation of Random forest and it provides a good accuracy than the other algorithms.

Figure 22: LU representation of 2007 spectral image Figure 23: LU representation of 2013 spectral image

The classified images of the two years can be enough to calculate the area of different land cover and land use and also it helps to observe the changes that are taking place in the range of data. The classified images obtained after pre-processing and Random forest DT classification that showing the land use and land cover of the Hyderabad city are given in the following figures Fig. 3, 4 and 5, 6.

The below table predicts that the difference between the training and test data found in 2007 and 2013 images in the form of performance accuracy, in which accuracy is divided for existing, proposed and user perspective and the overall accuracy and kappa statistics is also calculated as shown in table 2.

The accuracy of all the LC and LU classes are improved in our proposed system than the system and improved overall accuracy is also achieved, which is clearly represented in table 2.

LC & LU class	2007			2011		
	EXISTING ACCURACY	PROPOSED ACCURACY	USER'S ACCURACY	EXISTING ACCURACY	PROPOSED ACCURACY	USER'S ACCURACY
Water	98%	98%	100%	97%	97.2%	100%
Forest	88%	90%	75%	89%	91.1%	60%
Urban	28%	26%	71.43%	34%	35%	100%
Barren land	67%	67.06%	85%	78%	79.2%	75%
Overall Accuracy	71.33%	71.33%	71.33%	73.23%	73.73%	73.73
Kappa Statistic	0.49			0.56		

Table 2. Classification Accuracy Assessment Report

4.7 Analysis Report:

The distribution of LC &LU classes in the image should not be same all the time rather it will get changed regarding climate and weather condition. Generally, the water bodies region sometimes tend to form as barren land when it is summer and vice versa for rainy season. Likewise the barren land sometimes forms as forest area abruptly. The experimental results in our system also tend to change according to such natural phenomena. An assumption of climate is made in this research and a report is generated to denote the pixel occupancy of the classified LC and LU classes of 2007 and 2011, which is measured in hectares shown in table3.

Table 3: Analysis report of 2007 & 2013 land cover classes in hectares

LC &LU Class	2007 (ha)	2013 (ha)	2007-2013 (ha)
Water	5011.2	3323.17	-1688.04
Forest	9622.89	13200.06	+3577.17
Urban	6016.63	8665.1	+2648.47

Barren Land	23272.75	12311.06	-10961.68
Land Covr	15964.95	18743.08	+2778.125
Land Use	36441.62	18743.08	-17697.97

The calculation of LC and LU regions are given as LC= Forest + water, LU= Urban + barren land. The above mentioned table and calculation method depicts that, the land cover (LC) is of 85.0% because the water bodies is 66.3% and forest is 72.9%. Likewise the LU region becomes as 51.4% as the urban use is 69.4% and barren land is 52.8%. These generated values are for particular assumption of weather condition considered by us in this research. On the other hand the value of water and forest may become positive if the barren lands are occupied by more water or more forest.

5. Conclusion:

The paper is a source that reproduces the Urbanization assessment and analysis data with its improved Decision tree algorithm based on budget based calculation. The spectral and texture attributes are the major components constitutes the spatial feature system, is calculated and the band level differentiation were implemented to provide an improved classification system. The algorithm has been experimented by comparing it with the earlier methods and the reports are tabulated. The classification results of LC and LU regions from the tabulation, shows the rate of urbanization and different attributes of water, forest and barren lands in the years 2007 and 2013 as well. It is concluded by stating that the urbanization in Hyderabad region and its detection accuracy is improved by the proposed technique to a great extent.

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